

openmod Workshop 2023

Achievements and Challenges of the openmod

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Reiner Lemoine Institut

- Not-for-profit research institute
- 100 % subsidiary of Reiner Lemoine Foundation (RLS)
- Established 2010 in Berlin
- Managing Director: Dr. Kathrin Goldammer

Objective

Applied Research for 100% Renewable Energies

Scientific staff

~ 60 researchers and 40 students in 3 research fields

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Transformation of Energy Systems

Energy System Analysis

- Energy scenarios
- Sector coupling: electricity, heat, mobility
- Expansion scenarios

Power Grids

- Storage positioning
- Flexibility assessment
- Distribution grids

Data Management & Open Science

- Research Data Management
- Databases
- Data Processing
- Ontology and Knowledge Graphs

Visualisation & Participation

- Interactive maps & Tools
- Web interfaces
- Participation

Image not licensed!

openmod open energy
modelling **initiative**

What is the openmod?

- ❖ A bottom-up **grass root initiative** since 2014
- ❖ A **platform** to share information, code and data
- ❖ An **interest group** to lobby for transparency and openness
- ❖ A **network** to exchange results, ideas and problems
- ❖ A series of **workshops** and community events

What has the openmod?

Infrastructure:

- ❖ **Website** <https://openmod-initiative.org/>
- ❖ **Wiki** <https://wiki.openmod-initiative.org/>
- ❖ **Forum** <https://forum.openmod.org/>
- ❖ **Mailing List** <https://groups.google.com/g/openmod-initiative>

What has the openmod?

Accounts:

❖ YouTube

<https://www.youtube.com/@openmod-initiative/>

❖ GitHub

<https://github.com/openmod-initiative>

❖ Twitter

<https://twitter.com/openmod>

❖ Mastodon / Zenodo Group?

What makes it special?

❖ 10 Workshops!

❖ > 670 Participants

❖ > 133 Break-out-Group / Do-A-Thons

❖ > 143 Lightning Talks / Presentations

❖ > 10 Trainings

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Open Science - Energy System Modelling

„Open data, open source, and open access in relation to the energy modelling process.“
[Pfenninger et al. \(2018\)](#) licensed [CC BY 4.0](#)

Open Energy Family

Open Energy Family

Evolution of Infrastructures

❖ Model Factsheets

- Wiki openmod
 - 85 Models/ Frameworks

- OEP Factsheets
 - 24 Frameworks
 - 230 Models

- OEP Factsheets KG (alpha)
 - Using the Ontology and KG

The screenshot shows the 'openmod' website interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text 'Search' and a magnifying glass icon. Below the search bar is a navigation menu with options: 'Main page', 'Models', and 'Model implementations'. The main content area is titled 'Open Models' and includes a sub-section for 'Discussion'. A text block below the title states: 'This page lists energy models published under open source licenses. We regard licenses approved by OSI (opensource.org) and The Open Definition (opendefinition.org) as suitable for open source models and open data, respectively. Please contact us if you...'

The screenshot displays the 'Model Factsheets' interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links: 'Database', 'Factsheets', 'Ontology', 'Tutorials', and 'About'. Below this is a search bar with the text 'Search: oemof'. The main content is a table with the following columns: 'Name', 'acronym', 'primary purpose', 'open source', 'license', 'comment on geo resolution', 'short description of mathematical model class', and 'tags'. The table contains two entries for 'oemof' models. The first entry is 'oemof Application Brandenburg Berlin' with acronym 'oemof_abbb', primary purpose 'Simulation of the energy system in 2030 in the German region Brandenburg ...', open source 'true', license 'GNU Affero General Public License v3.0', comment 'Regionale Planungsgemeinschaften Brandenburg + Berlin', and tags 'oemof', 'oemof_abbb', 'GPL-3.0', '2030', '2017'. The second entry is 'oemof Brandenburg Berlin' with acronym 'oemof-B3', primary purpose 'Simulation of the energy system in the German region Brandenburg and Berlin.', open source 'true', license 'GNU Affero General Public License v3.0', and no comment or tags. To the right of the table is an 'Actions' section with a '+ Add Model' button and a 'Tags' section with a grid of year tags (2012-2024) and other tags like 'AG Technologiedate', 'Apache-2.0', 'Article', 'BMU', 'BMWK', and 'Beuth Hochschule'.

Evolution of Infrastructures

❖ Data Sets

- Wiki openmod
 - >100 Links (mostly broken)
- OPSD project (2015-2017)
 - 5 Data Packages
- OEMetadata Standard
 - Universal, flexible, easy
 - Ontology-Ready
- Energy Databus (open beta)
 - Central Metadata Repository
 - LOD + SPAQRL

openmod Search

Navigation

- Main page
- Models
- Model implementations
- Data
- Grid data

Page Discussion

Data

This is work in progress and is supposed to become a link list to sources of open energy-related data. We focus on collecting links to data relevant for the modelling of energy and electricity systems and markets. You are welcome to fill in the missing spots and non-existing pages. Also, you are welcome to extend the list of relevant data (e.g. for a European energy system model) that we should collect links to in the future.

Data requirements for a European energy system model

Energy Databus

RECENT ACTIVITY

Updated Data (USD)

SEARCH

Q wind turbine

- Wind Turbine Library
openmod > supply > wind_turbine_library
- RIJ - Danish Energy Agency - Technology Data for Generation of Electricity and District Heating - Technology Data Catalogue for Electricity and district heating production - Updated April 2020 - Wind Turbine (Selected Parameter)
ludex > dea-technology-data > rij-dea-td-generation-wind-turbine

❖ Glossary / Ontology

- Wiki openmod Glossary
 - 323 Terms
 - Definitions / Synonyms / Subterms
- Open Energy Ontology (OEO)
 - Upper-structure BFO
 - V1.13.0 (monthly releases)
 - 31 Contributors
 - 1430 Classes
 - 15180 Axioms

generating_capacity

- **Name:** generating_capacity
- **Description:** Generation capacity for one unit of the technology
- **Type:** real
- **Is_about:**

declared net capacity

- **Name:** declared net capacity
- **Path:** <https://openenergy-platf>
- **Unit:** MW

Class label: declared net capacity

Definition:

Declared net capacity is a power capacity stating the maximum power a power generating unit or a power plant can deliver to the electrical grid. It equals the sum of the rated powers of all plant generators minus all power used internally within the plant.

Sub classes:

block size

view

Super classes:

power capacity

view

Ontology

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Behaviour that contributes to a positive environment for our community:

- Demonstrating empathy and kindness toward other people
- Being respectful of differing opinions, viewpoints, and experiences
- Giving and gracefully accepting constructive feedback
- Accepting responsibility and apologizing to those affected by our mistakes, and learning from the experience
- Focusing on what is best not just for us as individuals, but for the overall community

- Participation at openmod workshops?
- Comments on the openmod forum?
- What is your main goal for the workshop?

„The opposite of **‘open’** isn’t **‘closed’**. The opposite of **‘open’** is **‘broken’**.“

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